

Automation of the Maritime UAV Command, Control, Navigation Operations, Simulated in Real-Time Using Kinect Sensor: A Feasibility Study

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Abstract—This paper describes the process used in the automation of the Maritime UAV commands using the Kinect sensor. The AR Drone is a Quadrocopter manufactured by Parrot [1] to be controlled using the Apple operating systems such as iPhones and I pads. However, this project uses the Microsoft Kinect SDK and Microsoft Visual Studio C# (C sharp) software, which are compatible with Windows Operating System for the automation of the navigation and control of the AR drone.

The navigation and control software for the Quadrocopter runs on a windows 7 computer. The project is divided into two sections; the Quadrocopter control system and the Kinect sensor control system. The Kinect sensor is connected to the computer using a USB cable from which commands can be sent to and from the Kinect sensors. The AR drone has Wi-Fi capabilities from which it can be connected to the computer to enable transfer of commands to and from the Quadrocopter.

The project was implemented in C#, a programming language that is commonly used in the automation systems. The language was chosen because there are more libraries already established in C# for both the AR drone and the Kinect sensor.

The study will contribute toward research in automation of systems using the Quadrocopter and the Kinect sensor for navigation involving a human operator in the loop. The prototype created has numerous applications among which include the inspection of vessels such as ship, airplanes and areas that are not accessible by human operators.

Keywords—UAV, AR drone, Kinect Sensors, Automation, Real time, C sharp, Microsoft Kinect SDK.

I. INTRODUCTION

UNMANNED Aerial Vehicles, (UAV), are important in the Aerospace research industry because of their potential applications. The unmanned vehicles are becoming increasingly popular because of their ability to fly into areas that are not accessible by human operators (Mariusz Wzorek, 2006). These aerial vehicles are cheap and readily available depending on their application. Often times, researchers continue to build upon the vehicles adding on additional payload to carry out the desired tasks at hand. There are several types of UAV however this paper will concentrate on

the Quadrocopter. Quadrocopters are VTOL, Vertical Takeoff and Landing. This kind of vehicle is useful in areas where there is limited take off area such as on top of buildings or on a ship.

In the area of Mechatronics and Aerospace engineering Robotics and automation is a continuous research area which involves implementing system that imitate the way humans perceive information. Most research has been carried out in the areas involving the use of autonomous vehicles to investigate stereo vision sensors and how they are used to imitate human vision. Kumano et al (2000) researched the various methods that could be used in transmitting real time data as perceived by the autonomous mobile robot. The data transmitted is then used by the robot to avoid any obstacles in its mapped path. However, the Kinect depth sensors are used in the automation of the system translating the gestures into maneuvers.

This project uses a “parrot AR. Drone”, a quadrocopter that was created as a gaming platform for aviation lovers of all ages. This platform slowly became integrated in the research study environment and as such is being modified by developers, contributing in the area of aerospace enormously (Adam Salamon, 2008)[2]. In this project the quadrocopter is being used as a research tool to aid research.

The project consists of a communication network made up of a quadrocopter, “parrot AR. Drone”, “Kinect sensor” and a laptop. The aim of the project is to automate the procedures for navigation and control of the quadrocopter using the “Kinect sensor”. The prototype could be used in various areas and departments. The project has been designed to support operators to identify or mark out objects in remote locations. This is made possible by the camera system onboard of the drone which can be navigated and controlled remotely by the operator. The data obtained could then be used for further research. The prototype would be used to inspect vessels such as ships, airplanes, or areas that are affected by bush fires and report back the findings in real time. The data transmitted would enable the ground operators to access the situation on the ground, enabling appropriate actions and tactics to be applied to the situation at hand.

In recent studies, the Kinect sensors have been used for robotic vision and control because the sensors can be utilized to transmit and integrate the human movements and actions in the control loop of the autonomous vehicles in real time. The Microsoft Kinect 360 sensors have two monochrome CCD cameras equipped with 90 degree wide-angle lenses [7]. John

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Fig. 4 Microsoft Kinect Sensor

The Kinect sensor uses the different sensors to recognize and track the human body. The data tracked is used for the game console. The Kinect sensor together with the Kinect 360 console was designed for game environment. However, this paper describes how the data extracted from the Kinect sensor is used in the automation and the control of the UAV, AR. Drone incorporating real time pilot control of the quadcopter.

The *Infrared (IR) Camera* known as the RGB camera detects the **R**ed, **G**reen and **B**lue color components of an image it captures. The color VGA video camera assists in the recognition on facial features and other features by detecting the three colors. The *Infrared (IR) laser Projector*, is a depth sensor which works together with a monochrome CMOS (complimentary metal-oxide semiconductor). It projects its surroundings in 3-D regardless of the lighting. [3]. The Kinect also contains *Multi-array microphones* that isolate the players' voice from that of the background. It is essential for the player to be stationed a few feet from the Kinect sensor, allowing the Kinect to work efficiently. The sensor's depth and video cameras have a 640 x 480 pixel resolutions that are run at 30 frames per second. This feature allows the videos and data transmitted by the Kinect to be transmitted in real time [3].

III. AUTOMATION AND CONTROL

Proposed system:

This section discusses the entire system and how the separate subsystems communicate with each other and the type of data transferred to and from each subsystem.

Fig. 5 The PROPOSED system

Fig. 5, shows the entire system implemented and how each sub block communicates with the other. The AR. Drone Wi-Fi capabilities enable it to connect to the computer with wireless capabilities. The AR. Drone is powered by a LiPo battery with a flight time competence of 12- when flying at a speed of 5 meters/second (16.4 feet per second) [4].

The Kinect sensor is connected to the computer via a USB cable. The Kinect sensor needs to be powered to a power source. The availability of the Kinect sensor and AR. Drone

libraries allows the transfer of data to and from the computer. The data from the Kinect sensor in the form of gestures is transferred to the AR. Drone wirelessly to enable the control of the quadcopter.

The computer acts as the interface between the quadcopter and the Kinect sensor. An automation program implemented in C# runs on the computer and when started, connects to both the quadcopter and the sensor as shown in the flow diagram in Fig. 6, below.

Fig. 6 The System State Diagram

The flow chart shows the steps and the data flow within the program used to automate the control of the AR. Drone with the aid of the Kinect sensor with a human in the loop.

Automation procedure

The automation procedure uses the depth image data of the Kinect sensor and converts it to skeletal data. From skeletal data, joint information is extracted and used for various gestures. Each joint is allocated within the space, x, y and z coordinates making it accessible for use and data allocation. The coordinate on which the skeletal data is based is a representation of the 3-D full skeleton;

Fig. 7 Kinect Sensor Skeletal data coordinate system and Joint data [10]

IV. GESTURES

Using the skeletal and joints' data obtained from the Kinect, the gestures described below are used as signals that are sent to the AR. Drone to control and maneuver the quadcopter.

The gestures are captured by the depth sensors by taking the coordinates of the joints that are used. The x, y and z coordinates of the joints are used to control the AR. Drone. However the AR. Drone states are calculated between -1 and 1 and the values are then sent to the Drone using the UDP single packets. The values between -1 and 1 represent the speed of the Drone of its configured power [11].

For example:

A command to be sent to the AR. Drone for the float 0.1 of the configured power of the drone would be sent in the form of a 32-bit integer. However the conversion would be carried out as follows; [1] & [4].

(Float) 0.1-> (hexadecimal) 3DCCCCCD-> (32-bit integer) 1036831949

TABLE I
OPERATOR GESTURES CAPTURED BY SENSORS

Command	Human Gesture	Sensor Gesture using IR Laser Projector
Takeoff		
Land		
Right		
Left		

Forward

Backward

Example Algorithm in C#

```

If ((leftHand Y > leftElbowY and rightHand Y > rightElbow Y ))
{
    Return String.Format ("AT*PCMD= %d, 1, 0, 1065353216, 0, 0", sequenceNumber)
    // Quadrocopter (Drone moves backwards)
}
Else if ((leftHand Y > leftElbow Y and rightHand Y > rightElbow Y ))
{
    Return String.Format ("AT*REF= {0}, {1}\r", sequenceNumber, 290718208);
    // Quadrocopter (Drone Takeoff)
}

Else if (rightHand X > rightElbow X)
{
    Return String.Format ("AT*PCMD= %d, 1, 1065353216, 0, 0, 0", sequenceNumber); //roll right
    // Quadrocopter (Drone turns right)
}
Else if (rightHand X<rightElbow X && leftHand X < leftElbow X)
{
    return String.Format("AT*PCMD= {0},{1},{3},{4},{5}\r", sequenceNumber,1, -1082130432,0,0,0);
    // Quadrocopter (Drone) turns Left
}
    
```

The sample code provided shows a sample of different commands that have been sent from the Kinect to the Drone and the actions that are executed.

V. RESULTS

Fig. 8 Takeoff and Left control results

VI. CONCLUSION

The paper describes the methodology used to automate the control and navigation system of the AR. Drone with the use of the Kinect depth sensor. The automation procedure transfers data from the pilot in real time. The data in gesture form is translated into quadcopter maneuvers. The intelligent system has been tested indoors. It also went through a number of real time outdoor trials and, due to the usefulness of the system, is going through a number of improvements as a future development plan.

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